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Urban wildlife as a reservoir of zoonotic pathogens: A multi-pathogen qPCR survey from a Central European City

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Abstract:	<p>Urbanisation alters wildlife communities and creates “epidemiological bridges” between wild, domestic, and synanthropic hosts. Data on multiple pathogen taxa circulating simultaneously in urban mammals in Central Europe remain limited. Between July 2023 and July 2025, 240 wild mammals (native and invasive) were collected in the urban and peri-urban district of Brno, Czech Republic. Intestinal content, tongue, lymph nodes and other organs were examined using multiplex qPCRs for selected viral, bacterial and parasitic pathogens, including hepatitis E virus (HEV), Francisella tularensis, Echinococcus multilocularis, Toxoplasma gondii, Toxocara spp., Baylisascaris procyonis and others. Basic statistical analyses were used to explore risk factors and co-infections. Overall, 43.3% animals were positive for at least one pathogen. Multiple tissue positivity either with the same or more pathogens was observed. The work showed first molecular evidence of HEV and F. tularensis in free-ranging European raccoon dogs, and HEV in stray cats. Highest prevalence was observed for Toxocara sp. in cats and red foxes. E. multilocularis, Toxocara spp. and B. procyonis were detected across several hosts. Strong associations were found between Toxocara and B. procyonis in cats and between Giardia duodenalis and Cryptosporidium parvum in cats. Age was identified as a significant factor with young foxes being infected more frequently by Toxocara than adults. These findings indicate substantial pathogen circulation and environmental contamination within urban adapted mammals. The pilot study provides a multi-pathogen baseline for urban wildlife in Central Europe and underscores the need for integrated, long-term One Health surveillance.</p>

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- Multi-pathogen qPCR survey reveals high pathogen circulation in urban wildlife
- First detection of HEV and *Francisella tularensis* in free-living raccoon dogs
- First evidence of HEV RNA shedding in a domestic, stray cat
- Findings provide a baseline for One Health surveillance in urban ecosystems

Urban wildlife as a reservoir of zoonotic pathogens: A multi-pathogen qPCR survey from a Central European City

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Declaration of Interest statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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1 **Abstract**

2

3 Urbanisation alters wildlife communities and creates “epidemiological bridges” between wild,
4 domestic, and synanthropic hosts. Data on multiple pathogen taxa circulating simultaneously
5 in urban mammals in Central Europe remain limited. Between July 2023 and July 2025, 240
6 wild mammals (native and invasive) were collected in the urban and peri-urban district of Brno,
7 Czech Republic. Intestinal content, tongue, lymph nodes and other organs were examined using
8 multiplex qPCRs for selected viral, bacterial and parasitic pathogens, including hepatitis E virus
9 (HEV), *Francisella tularensis*, *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Toxocara*
10 *spp.*, *Baylisascaris procyonis* and others. Basic statistical analyses were used to explore risk
11 factors and co-infections. Overall, 43.3% animals were positive for at least one pathogen.
12 Multiple tissue positivity either with the same or more pathogens was observed. The work
13 showed first molecular evidence of HEV and *F. tularensis* in free-ranging European raccoon
14 dogs, and HEV in stray cats. Highest prevalence was observed for *Toxocara sp.* in cats and red
15 foxes. *E. multilocularis*, *Toxocara spp.* and *B. procyonis* were detected across several hosts.
16 Strong associations were found between *Toxocara* and *B. procyonis* in cats and between *Giardia*
17 *duodenalis* and *Cryptosporidium parvum* in cats. Age was identified as a significant factor with
18 young foxes being infected more frequently by *Toxocara* than adults. These findings indicate
19 substantial pathogen circulation and environmental contamination within urban adapted
20 mammals. The pilot study provides a multi-pathogen baseline for urban wildlife in Central
21 Europe and underscores the need for integrated, long-term One Health surveillance.

22

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25

26 **1. Introduction**

27 Rapid urbanization and the growing human use of natural areas for agriculture and
28 recreation have reduced the availability of wildlife habitats, bringing wild mammals into more
29 frequent contact with humans and domestic animals.

30 Urban or suburban environments provide unique ecological conditions for wildlife,
31 including diverse shelter opportunities, reliable and predictable anthropogenic food resources,
32 and reduced predation pressure (Bateman and Fleming, 2012). A recent study from North
33 Carolina demonstrated a higher diversity of mammalian species in suburban areas compared to
34 nearby natural habitats underscoring the great adaptability of both predator and prey to human-
35 modified landscapes (Parsons et al., 2018). At the same time, urban and suburban environments
36 impose substantial ecological pressures, including habitat fragmentation, barriers to gene flow,
37 increased mortality from traffic, human-induced disturbances, direct persecution, and elevated
38 exposure to infectious agents (Ordeñana et al., 2010). Among anthropogenic forces,
39 urbanization stands out as a key driver reshaping ecological networks and pathogen dynamics.
40 Increased host density, artificial feeding opportunities and the absence of natural predators
41 intensify contact rates among wild, domestic, and synanthropic species, forming so-called
42 “epidemiological bridges” that enhance the probability of cross-species transmission (Albery
43 et al., 2022). In addition, urban microclimates characterized by higher temperatures, humidity
44 stability and organic enrichment can extend environmental survival of many pathogens
45 (Bradley and Altizer, 2007; Johnson et al., 2010). These processes create persistent and spatially
46 embedded pathogen reservoirs within the urban matrix.

47 Physiological stressors specific to cities—chemical pollution, noise, light-at-night
48 exposure, and altered diet—can modulate immune function and microbiome composition in
49 wild mammals (Giraudeau et al., 2024). Such stress-induced immunosuppression may increase
50 susceptibility to co-infections, partially explaining the high pathogen richness observed in

51 urban-adapted species (Becker et al., 2015; Albery et al., 2022). From a One Health perspective,
52 these findings illustrate that urban environments function as interconnected systems in which
53 the health of humans, domestic animals, and wildlife is closely linked.

54 In recent years, wild mesocarnivores, mainly red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) and mustelids, such
55 as badgers (*Meles meles*) and martens (*Martes foina*, *Martes martes*) have become more common
56 in proximity of human environments in Europe. Overabundant wild boar (*Sus scrofa*)
57 populations and the spread of invasive species such as raccoons (*Procyon lotor*), racoon dogs
58 (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*), and nutrias (*Myocastor coypus*) further accelerate this trend
59 (Schally et al., 2024). These generalist species are highly adaptable to a wide range of urban
60 niches and may act as multi-pathogen reservoirs, maintaining several zoonotic and veterinary-
61 relevant agents (Veronesi et al., 2023).

62 Urban-adapted mammals often harbour a higher overall diversity of pathogens than their
63 non-urban counterparts (Albery et al., 2022). This pattern is linked to urbanization-related
64 factors such as pollution, altered nutrition, and chronic stress that negatively modulate immune
65 responses (Becker et al., 2015). Greater host densities further promote density-dependent
66 transmission (Lloyd-Smith et al., 2005). Although a disproportionate share of zoonotic
67 pathogens has not been conclusively demonstrated in urban species, the absolute risk of
68 spillover increases with the total number of circulating pathogens (Albery et al., 2022). The
69 intensification of human–wildlife interactions in densely populated environments therefore
70 poses an increasing challenge for both veterinary and public health sectors.

71 Several studies have investigated the prevalence of parasitic, viral, or bacterial agents in
72 wildlife; however, most have focused on animals sampled in natural habitats such as wilderness
73 areas or national parks (Umhang et al., 2016; Foti et al., 2018; Omeragic et al., 2024). Some
74 research has addressed zoonoses in urban wildlife, but many relied on samples collected in
75 tourist destinations, such as islands, whose environmental characteristics are more rural than

76 urban (Waindok et al., 2021). Other works have targeted multiple pathogens but examined only
77 a single mammalian host species, such as raccoons (Reinhardt et al., 2023) or stray cats
78 (Mohsen and Hossein, 2009). Conversely, several studies have adopted the opposite approach,
79 surveying a broad range of wildlife hosts while focusing on a single pathogen, most commonly
80 *Toxoplasma* spp. (Dakroub et al., 2023; Matas Mendez et al., 2023), *Trichinella* (Hill et al.,
81 2008), *Echinococcus* (Knapp et al., 2018) or *Enterobacteriaceae* (Foti et al., 2018).

82 To date, studies simultaneously addressing multiple pathogen taxa across diverse urban
83 mammalian hosts remain scarce, particularly in Central Europe. Meanwhile, invasive
84 mesocarnivores continue to expand throughout Central and Eastern Europe, frequently
85 interacting with domestic animals and thereby increasing the need for comprehensive urban
86 wildlife surveillance (Nguyen et al., 2025). Understanding the ecological and epidemiological
87 roles of these species is critical for developing targeted prevention and control strategies within
88 the One Health framework. By integrating molecular screening with ecological context, this
89 study assesses the prevalence of selected bacterial, parasitic, and viral pathogens in wild
90 animals inhabiting the urban environment of Brno, a medium-sized Central European city. The
91 research includes both native and invasive species and emphasizes zoonotic agents relevant to
92 companion animals and public health.

93

94 **2. Materials and Methods**

95 *2.1. Sample collection*

96 Animal samples were obtained in cooperation with state nature conservation authorities,
97 wildlife rescue and capture services, municipal police officers, and local hunting associations.
98 Sampling was conducted as part of routine wildlife management, population control, and
99 collection of road-killed animals, all under permits issued by the competent authorities. Only

100 carcasses of animals found dead or legally culled were included in the study; no animal was
101 euthanized for research purposes.

102 All samples originated from the district of Brno-mesto, Czech Republic, which covers
103 230.2 km² and consists of a mosaic of urban and peri-urban habitats, including densely built
104 residential areas, industrial sites, city parks, and adjacent forested patches. Fieldwork was
105 conducted between 1 July 2023 and 30 July 2025, thus spanning two complete annual cycles to
106 reflect possible seasonal variation in wildlife occurrence.

107 Each carcass was identified to species; its sex and age were determined based on dentition
108 and overall body condition. To maintain sample integrity and avoid post-mortem decay, only
109 freshly deceased animals were used. Carcasses were included only when no visible signs of
110 decomposition were present, and sampling was generally performed within two hours of
111 discovery, provided that the estimated post-mortem interval did not exceed this limit. All field
112 procedures were carried out by trained personnel following standard biosafety measures for
113 handling potentially zoonotic material. For each specimen, geographic coordinates, collection
114 date, locality, and presumed cause of death were documented.

115 In total, 240 animals were examined. From each, a sample of intestinal content was
116 obtained, except for one fox in which the intestine was unavailable (n = 239). Every effort was
117 made to collect tongue and lymph node samples from all individuals. However, this was not
118 possible in some cases due to carcass condition, particularly in road-killed animals with severe
119 trauma. When pathological findings were suspected, additional tissues such as liver or lungs
120 were taken (Table 1). All samples were frozen immediately and stored at -70 °C until further
121 processing.

122

123 *2.2. DNA and RNA isolation*

124 DNA from faecal samples was isolated by the Quick-DNA Fecal/Soil Microbe Miniprep
125 Kit (Zymo Research, USA) according to the manufacturer's manual. Sample pretreatment
126 included homogenization 150 mg of faeces with the 750 μ l of Bashing buffer, 5×10^5 molecules
127 of IAC DNA and the Bashing beads provided in the Zymo kit using an Omni Bead Ruptor Elite
128 (Omni International, Kennesaw, GA, USA) at 6 m/s for 1 min. The isolated DNA was eluted
129 twice by 50 μ l of elution buffer in order to increase the yield of isolated DNA resulting in total
130 volume of 100 μ l of the eluted DNA. This volume was additionally cleaned up on the Zymo-
131 Spin III-HRC column (Zymo Research). RNA from faecal samples was isolated by the
132 QIAamp® Viral RNA kit (Qiagen, Germany). Isolation was performed from the 10%
133 suspension of homogenized and centrifuged faeces prepared in PBS, pH 7.2. The IAC RNA *in*
134 *vitro* transcript was used as previously described (Vasickova et al., 2012).

135 DNA from tissue samples, regardless of origin (lymph nodes, tongue, suspected lesions,
136 internal organs), was isolated using the DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen) following the
137 manufacturer's protocol for tissues. Approximately 100 mg of tissue were placed to the 2 ml
138 screw cap tube and mixed with the 400 μ l of the ATL buffer, 40 μ l of proteinase K, 5×10^5
139 molecules of IAC DNA and 400 mg of the 0.1 mm and 400 mg of the 2.3 mm zirconia/silica
140 beads (Biospec, USA). This suspension was homogenized using Omni Bead Ruptor Elite at 6
141 m/s for 1 min, then shortly spun, incubated at 56°C for 30 min and then centrifuged at 13 000 g
142 \times 3 min. The entire supernatant, excluding the beads, was transferred to a new tube. DNA
143 purification was performed according to the manufacturer's manual, with the volume of AL
144 buffer and ethanol adjusted proportionally. Similarly to faecal samples, DNA from tissue
145 samples was eluted in two subsequent steps with 75 μ l of the Elution buffer yielding a final
146 volume of 150 μ l. The IAC was prepared and used as described above (Vojkovska et al., 2015).

147

148 2.3. *qPCR analysis*

149 The species analysed with regard to the type of sample matrix are listed in Table 2. The
150 detection of the pathogens was performed using previously published primers and probes (Table
151 3; (Malorny et al., 2004; Fujita et al., 2006; Slana et al., 2008; Atterby et al., 2009; Gatcombe
152 et al., 2010; Helmi et al., 2011; Durant et al., 2012; Lass et al., 2012; Vasickova et al., 2012;
153 Knapp et al., 2014)). To improve the effectiveness of the analyses the original singleplex qPCR
154 assays were multiplexed as follows: HEV multiplex (two independent targets within HEV
155 genome), CGE multiplex (*Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Giardia duodenalis*, *Echinococcus*
156 *multilocularis*), TOXTRIF multiplex (*Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trichinella spiralis*, *Francisella*
157 *tularensis/holarctica*) and BATO multiplex (*Baylisascaris procyonis*, *Toxocara canis/cati*).
158 Previously published multiplex qPCR assay for the detection of *Mycobacterium avium* subsp.
159 *avium* and *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *hominissuis* (MYCO multiplex; (Dziedzinska et al.,
160 2025) and *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* (MAP multiplex; (Slana et al., 2008)
161 were also used in the analysis. The IAC was included with the MYCO and HEV multiplexes.
162 Finally, selected samples were analysed for the presence of the *Mycobacterium bovis*
163 (EliGene® MTB UNI, ELISABETH PHARMACON, Czech Republic) and *Salmonella*
164 *enterica* subsp. *enterica* (Malorny et al., 2004). The qPCR multiplexes (except of the HEV
165 multiplex and MTB UNI) were based on the generic premix preparation protocol, which were
166 mixed according to the following formula: 10 µl of the EliZyme™ Probe MIX (ELISABETH
167 PHARMACON), 500 nM of each primer and 250 nM of each probe (the organization of the
168 multiplexes is described in Table 3). Total reaction volume was 20 µl and 2 µl of isolated DNA
169 was always added to the mix.

170 The HEV multiplex was prepared according to the published protocol (Vasickova et al.,
171 2012). Isolated RNA (5 µl) was mixed with 5 µl of the mixture containing 10 nmol of dNTPs
172 and 200 nM of reverse primers (JVHEVR,TqRev and IS900qPCRR). The mixture was
173 denatured at 65 °C for 5 min, followed by immediate chilling on ice. Subsequently, the 5×

174 PrimeScript Buffer, 100 U of PrimeScript Reverse Transcriptase (Takara, Japan), 20 U of
175 Ribonuclease Inhibitor (Takara) and RNase-free water was added to the chilled mixture of
176 primers and RNA to the total volume of 20 μ l. The RT reaction was performed at 50°C for 60
177 min, followed by inactivation at 75°C for 15 min. The multiplex qPCR for HEV consisted of
178 10 μ l of the EliZyme™ Probe MIX (ELISABETH PHARMACON), 200 nM of each primer
179 and 100 nM of each probe in total reaction volume was 20 μ l with 2 μ l of cDNA added to the
180 mix.

181 All analyses were performed on a LightCycler® 480 Real-Time PCR instrument (Roche
182 Molecular Diagnostics, Germany). The qPCR analysis of the HEV, CGE, TOXTRIF, BATO
183 multiplexes and *S. enterica* assay were performed under the following conditions: initial
184 denaturation step at 95°C for 3 minutes, followed by 47 cycles at 95°C for 5 seconds, 55°C for
185 10 seconds (fluorescence collection) and 72°C for 10 seconds. The MAP and MYCO
186 multiplexes was run under following conditions: initial denaturation step at 95°C for 3 minutes,
187 followed by 47 cycles at 95°C for 5 seconds and 60°C for 30 seconds (fluorescence collection).
188 The qPCR reactions were then cooled to 40°C for 30 seconds. *Mycobacterium bovis* detection
189 was performed according to the manufacturer's protocol. The downstream analysis was
190 performed using the "Fit point analysis" option of the LightCycler 480 software (version
191 1.5.0.39). Each DNA sample was tested in biological triplicate by each qPCR assay. The mean
192 of the three C_q values was subsequently used in the qualitative analysis.

193 Standards for almost all the qPCR target organisms were synthesized *de novo in vitro*
194 (Eurofins Genomics, Germany). The synthesized single stranded fragments were mixed
195 together to the final concentration of 35 fM of each, i.e. 2×10^4 ssDNA or RNA fragments in
196 1 μ l. This universal standard was used in HEV, CGE, TOXTRIF, BATO multiplexes as a
197 positive control. Positive control for *Mycobacterium bovis* detection was included the

198 commercial kit (EliGene® MTB UNI) or were used as described previously (Dziedzinska et
199 al., 2025).

200

201 2.4. Statistical analysis

202 Differences in distances from carcasses to built-up areas, dust-bin sites, green areas, or
203 water bodies between pathogen-positive and pathogen-negative animals were tested using the
204 Mann-Whitney U test. Fisher's exact test was used to assess differences in pathogen occurrence
205 between adult and juvenile animals and to test for association between pathogen occurrences.
206 The Phi coefficient was used as a measure of pathogen co-occurrence.

207

208 3. Results and Discussion

209 Out of 240 examined animals, 104 (43.3%) harboured at least one pathogen in at least one
210 tissue. In total, 115 samples tested positive (115/758; 15.2%), indicating that some animals
211 showed positivity in multiple tissues. The intestine represented the most frequent site of
212 detection, with 90 of 115 positive samples (78.3%). Among animals with multi-tissue positivity,
213 intestinal content was most frequently involved, typically in combination with liver, tongue, or
214 lymph nodes, highlighting the intestine as the primary site of pathogen detection in urban
215 mammals.

216 One of the most notable results was a raccoon dog exhibiting simultaneous positivity in
217 three tissues—intestine, tongue, and lymph nodes. Such co-occurrences across distinct tissue
218 types suggest either a systemic exposure or multiple independent acquisition events. The
219 raccoon dog was among the three animals with HEV detected in the intestine; intriguingly, its
220 tongue and lymph nodes were positive for *Francisella tularensis* (Table 4), a highly pathogenic
221 and epidemiologically important zoonotic agent.

222 Among the four subspecies of *F. tularensis*, type A (*F. tularensis* subsp. *tularensis*) and type
223 B (*F. tularensis* subsp. *holarctica*) are the most pathogenic for humans. While *F. tularensis* type
224 A occurs in North America, type B is restricted to Europe, where rabbits and rodents constitute
225 primary hosts in the terrestrial cycle, and beavers and muskrats play a major role in the aquatic
226 cycle. Several cases of human tularaemia have been reported across Europe, including the
227 Czech Republic, with wild hares and rodents considered the primary sources of infection
228 (Carvalho et al., 2014). To date, *F. tularensis* has not been detected in raccoon dogs in the Czech
229 Republic. In Europe, seropositive raccoon dogs have been documented in Germany, Sweden,
230 and Denmark (Kuehn et al., 2013; Hestvik et al., 2019; Hansen et al., 2025). However, to our
231 knowledge, no study has yet provided direct molecular or culture-based evidence of
232 *F. tularensis* in European raccoon dogs. This finding is therefore notable, as *F. tularensis* has
233 not been previously reported in this species in Europe, suggesting a possible spillover event or
234 environmental contamination. A single PCR-positive finding in lung tissue from a raccoon dog
235 was reported in the United States in 2011 (Duncan et al., 2012). Given their omnivorous diet,
236 including consumption of rodents and carrion such as hares, raccoon dogs may represent a
237 potential host species (Sutor et al., 2010) and, according to our data, we suggest it could serve
238 as potential hosts and sentinels for *F. tularensis* circulation in wildlife.

239 Additionally to *F. tularensis*, our study also provides evidence of hepatitis E virus (HEV)
240 circulation in urban carnivores. We corroborate a recent investigation from China reporting the
241 first molecular evidence of hepatitis E virus (HEV) in farmed raccoon dogs (Tian et al., 2024).
242 Although HEV-specific antibodies have been detected in 34.3% of European raccoon dogs,
243 viral RNA has not previously been identified (Dähnert et al., 2018). The presence of HEV RNA
244 in a wild raccoon dog in our study (Table 4) thus represents the first direct indication of active
245 infection in this species in Europe. Moreover, HEV RNA was detected in the faeces of a
246 domestic cat (Table 4)—the first such evidence according to the author’s knowledge—

247 demonstrating that felids can actively shed the virus, extending earlier serological evidence of
248 exposure (Liang et al., 2014; Caballero-Gómez et al., 2022). While based on limited
249 observations, these findings collectively suggest that both raccoon dogs and domestic cats may
250 contribute to environmental contamination with HEV, underscoring the need for targeted
251 surveillance to clarify their role in the epidemiology of this zoonotic virus.

252 In agreement with previous studies, our findings further support the role of raccoon dogs
253 as reservoirs of *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Bagrade et al., 2016; Pilarczyk et al., 2022).
254 *E. multilocularis* DNA was found in livers of 2 of 12 raccoon dogs; in one of them with
255 concurrent finding of *E. multilocularis* in intestine. Similar hepatic detections have been
256 reported in domestic dogs (Peregrine et al., 2012) and in rare cases, both hepatic metacestodes
257 and adult intestinal stages have been observed simultaneously (Deplazes and Eckert, 2001).
258 Several mechanisms, such as ingestion of infective eggs, prior intestinal infection, or internal
259 autoinfection have been proposed to explain liver involvement (Deplazes and Eckert, 2001).
260 However, as our findings were not confirmed histologically, the underlying pathway cannot be
261 determined with certainty. Overall, the growing abundance and long-distance dispersal capacity
262 of raccoon dogs in Europe suggests that, this invasive species may contribute to the
263 maintenance and spread of emerging and re-emerging zoonoses, with possible consequences
264 for both human and animal health.

265 *Toxocara canis/cati* was the most frequently pathogen detected in intestine (38/239; 15.9%)
266 with highest prevalence found in cats (30.6%; 22/72), and foxes (22%; 10/45). Both species
267 play key role in life cycle and transmission of *Toxocara*. Across Europe, the prevalence of
268 *T. canis* in red foxes reaches 34.6% (Holland et al., 2024) while *T. cati* occurs in 17% of pet
269 cats and 28.6% of stray cats (Rostami et al., 2020). Stray cats pose a higher risk of
270 environmental contamination with *Toxocara* eggs because outdoor lifestyles greatly increase
271 the eggs shedding (Nijssen et al., 2016). From a zoonotic perspective, *T. cati* may pose a greater

272 risk than *T. canis*. Eggs of *T. cati* exhibit higher tolerance to freezing, and this resilience is
273 reinforced by the habit of cats burying their faeces. *T. cati* also utilises a wider range of paratenic
274 hosts, and cats frequently defecate in gardens, vegetable plots, and sandpits (Maciag et al.,
275 2022). Moreover, owners are generally more consistent in removing dog faeces than cat faeces.
276 Together, these ecological and behavioural traits likely contribute to the consistently higher
277 recovery of *T. cati* eggs in urban environmental samples compared with *T. canis* (Tyungu et al.,
278 2020; Maciag et al., 2022). In New York City, the environmental contamination ranged from 30
279 to 67%, exclusively with *T. cati* (Tyungu et al., 2020). *T. cati* was detected in 85% of sandpits
280 and 50% of parks, whereas *T. canis* was found in only 12.5% of sandpits and 3.9% of parks
281 (Otero et al., 2018).

282 *Toxocara* spp. have a broad range of paratenic hosts, with detection possible in both
283 intestinal contents and tissues, most commonly the liver (Holland, 2023). In Europe, *T. canis*
284 has been sporadically reported in faeces of raccoons and raccoon dogs (Pilarczyk et al., 2022;
285 Reinhardt et al., 2023). Although a high affinity of *Toxocara* spp. to liver is well recognised,
286 detections in the livers of free-ranging wildlife have not been documented, except for
287 experimental infections. In our study *T. canis/cati* DNA was demonstrated in the livers of three
288 badgers (3/13) and one raccoon (Table 4). As classical parasitology and histology were not
289 included, the molecular finding alone cannot confirm larval migration or encystation in these
290 species, nor establish badgers and raccoons as paratenic hosts of *T. canis/T. cati*. However,
291 contamination during sampling can be excluded, as *Toxocara* DNA was detected exclusively in
292 liver tissue and was absent from intestinal samples from the same individuals. Additionally, no
293 *Toxocara* was found in other animals collected on the same day ruling out cross-contamination
294 from sampling instruments (e.g. dissecting knives).

295 Since 1990, the raccoon populations have increased by approximately 300% in Central
296 Europe, leading to the establishment of stable populations across several European countries.

297 Due to their rapid population growth and range expansion, raccoons are considered invasive in
298 most of Europe, with documented negative impacts on native wildlife species (Salgado, 2018).
299 Together with other neozoa, they are of concern as potential reservoirs of zoonotic pathogens.
300 Raccoons are the definitive host of the zoonotic roundworm *Baylisascaris procyonis*, with
301 reported prevalences in Europe ranging from 33% to as high as 95% (Heddergott et al., 2020;
302 Lombardo et al., 2022; Maas et al., 2022; Peter et al., 2023). In our study, *B. procyonis* was not
303 detected in raccoons; however, this finding should be interpreted with caution given the limited
304 number of raccoons examined (Table 1). *B. procyonis* DNA was, however, detected in wild
305 boars (7/42; 17%), cats, foxes (both 7%), and martens (5/17; 29%; Table 4). Because its DNA
306 was found only in intestinal content and none of the positive species are definitive hosts able to
307 shed eggs through faeces, the role of these paratenic hosts is negligible from zoonotic point of
308 view.

309 Raccoons shed unembryonated eggs of *B. procyonis* into the environment, which require
310 2–4 weeks to develop into infective stages. During the maturation period, eggs may be ingested
311 by various paratenic hosts, leading to larval migration and tissue infection. In our study,
312 *B. procyonis* DNA was detected exclusively in intestinal contents but not in tissues. This may
313 reflect ingestion of either non-embryonated (non-infective) or embryonated eggs, limited ability
314 of tissue sampling for detecting encysted larvae, or the fact that the examined organs were not
315 typical predilection sites for *B. procyonis*. Nevertheless, the detection of DNA in several animal
316 species indicates exposure to *B. procyonis* eggs and suggests an environmental burden within
317 the city or its close surroundings. According to Ogdee et al. (2017), a single infected raccoon
318 can contaminate approximately 0.03 ha of the environment with *B. procyonis* eggs within one
319 year (Ogdee et al., 2017). The eggs are extremely resistant, surviving months of desiccation and
320 high temperatures, while freezing has minimal effect on their viability (Shafir et al., 2011).
321 Overall, the combination of these factors points to *B. procyonis* as a notable zoonotic risk,

322 amplified by expanding raccoon populations and the increasing overlap between raccoon
323 habitats and human settlements.

324 Nutria was the last invasive species included in this study. The only pathogen detected in
325 them (20%) was *T. gondii*, which was found in the tongue, lymph nodes, and liver. *T. gondii* is
326 a zoonotic pathogen causing generally asymptomatic or non-specific symptoms in
327 immunocompetent individuals but can manifest as severe disease for unborn children and
328 immunocompromised individuals. Its prevalence range between 18 to 50 % within Europe, with
329 lowest prevalence in northern Europe and UK (Friesema et al., 2025). The consumption of raw
330 or undercooked meat raw milk and unwashed vegetables or shellfish contaminated with oocysts
331 represent the most risk factors (Thebault et al., 2021). Because nutrias are not the definitive
332 host of *T. gondii* and therefore do not shed infectious eggs into the environment, the only risk
333 would arise from consumption of undercooked nutria meat. As no other felid predators occur
334 in urban areas that would prey on nutria, they likely represent a dead-end host for the life cycle
335 of *T. gondii*.

336 Statistical analysis did not reveal any significant associations between the occurrence of
337 pathogen-positive animals and environmental factors, including proximity to built-up areas,
338 dust-bin sites, green areas, or water bodies. This lack of significance is likely attributable to the
339 limited number of samples within individual environmental categories (data not shown). Age,
340 however, was identified as a significant factor in foxes, with juvenile red foxes being infected
341 more frequently than adults ($P < 0.01$; Table 5). This finding is consistent with previous studies
342 reporting significantly higher prevalence of *T. canis* and *T. cati* in juvenile (<12 months) foxes
343 and cats (Rostami et al., 2020; Holland et al., 2024), which is attributed to the immature immune
344 system in young animals (Nijssen et al., 2016).

345 Multiple infections in wild animals are common and can have wide-ranging consequences
346 for the host, including impaired immunity, reduced body condition, altered metabolism, and

347 increased susceptibility to additional pathogens (Bordes and Morand, 2011). They may be
348 explained by several factors, such as age, sex, habitat, population density, weather, and others,
349 that simultaneously promote exposure to both agents. While the concurrent occurrence of some
350 pathogens does not necessarily indicate a biological link, distinct associations have been
351 documented in some cases (Barroso et al., 2023). For instance, a strong relationship between
352 gastrointestinal helminths and *M. bovis* infection has been demonstrated in European badgers,
353 suggesting that the presence of one infection increases susceptibility to the other (Kelly et al.,
354 2022). A similar pattern has been reported for *Giardia duodenalis* and *Cryptosporidium* co-
355 infection in domestic and wild canids, where infection with one protozoan increases the
356 likelihood of acquiring the other. This suggests that both pathogens may be shaped by
357 overlapping ecological or host-related risk factors (Mateusa et al., 2024). In our study, a
358 comparable co-infection with *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* pattern was
359 observed in cats ($P < 0.05$; Table 6). Co-occurrence of *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium* has also
360 been documented in brown rats, where environmental factors were suggested to facilitate the
361 co-occurrence of both pathogens (Hancke and Suarez, 2020).

362 Another strong association ($P < 0.01$) was revealed between *T. canis/cati* and *B. procyonis*
363 in cats (Table 6). Previous studies have shown that co-infections with multiple endoparasites
364 are common in felids: nearly 10% of cats harbour more than two endoparasites (Beugnet et al.,
365 2014) and 50–80% of *Toxocara*-infected cats carry additional gastrointestinal or cardio-
366 respiratory nematodes (Remesar et al., 2022). Such co-infections are not unusual and are
367 typically associated with younger age and outdoor access, both of which belong to risk factors
368 increasing the risk of infection (Beugnet et al., 2014). Environmental contamination with
369 nematode eggs is considered a major driver of infection risk due to the eggs' remarkable
370 persistence (Traversa, 2012). Wild carnivores, including foxes and raccoons, further amplify
371 this environmental burden by acting as reservoirs and contributing additional parasite eggs to

372 the surroundings (Traversa, 2012). In the United Kingdom, Taylor et al. (2015) demonstrated
373 that increased prevalence of cardiopulmonary nematodes in foxes correlated with rising case
374 numbers in domestic dogs, underscoring the epidemiological relevance of wildlife reservoirs
375 (Taylor et al., 2015). The strong association between *Toxocara* and *B. procyonis* positivity in
376 cats observed in our study likely reflects substantial environmental contamination within the
377 city, where both parasites circulate concurrently.

378 Although this study provides important insights, several limitations should be
379 acknowledged. The sample size was limited, as only wild animals from an urban district were
380 included, so mostly those found dead (e.g., roadkill) or captured. Additionally, carcasses dead
381 for more than 24 hours were excluded to avoid nucleic acid degradation, which further reduced
382 the number of animals. Second, the study demonstrated the presence of pathogen DNA/RNA,
383 but did not confirm active infection or associated pathological changes. However, this study
384 was designed as a pilot one, its findings should be viewed as an initial assessment of the
385 zoonotic burden of urban wildlife and as a basis for more detailed investigations in specific
386 species. Lastly, molecular methods introduced both strengths and weaknesses. While classical
387 parasitological approaches (e.g., faecal sedimentation, worm/oocyst counting) might identify a
388 greater number of positives due to larger processed volumes/weights, molecular assays
389 provided superior specificity, avoiding the misidentification that might occur with morphology-
390 based diagnostics (Bagraade et al., 2016; Xie et al., 2020). Moreover, when additional groups of
391 pathogenic agents such as viruses were included, as in our case, the use of molecular methods
392 became indispensable.

393

394 **4. Conclusion**

395 This study provides one of the first multi-pathogen assessments of urban and peri-urban
396 mammals in Central Europe, revealing substantial circulation of zoonotic and veterinary-

397 relevant agents within a densely populated city. Several native and invasive species including
398 red foxes, raccoon dogs, martens, and stray cats harboured pathogens of public-health concern.
399 Notable findings included the first molecular detection of hepatitis E virus and *Francisella*
400 *tularensis* in free-living raccoon dogs, first direct prove of HEV in stray cats, and occurrence
401 of *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxocara* spp., and *Baylisascaris procyonis* across multiple
402 hosts. These results underscore the capacity of urban-adapted mammals to maintain diverse
403 pathogens within a One Health context. Patterns of co-infection, such as the association
404 between *Toxocara* and *B. procyonis* indicate shared ecological drivers and high levels of
405 environmental contamination. Detection of parasite DNA in paratenic hosts, together with the
406 persistence of helminth eggs, highlights the potential for long-term pathogen reservoirs in urban
407 ecosystems.

408 Overall, this work provides a baseline for understanding zoonotic risks associated with
409 urban wildlife and emphasizes the need for targeted, long-term surveillance. Incorporating
410 pathogen co-regulation into predictive models, along with behavioural, spatial, and longitudinal
411 data, will be crucial for characterizing transmission pathways and informing One Health-
412 oriented management strategies.

413

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Table 1 Number of samples collected from animal species

	Faeces	Tongue	Lymph nodes	Liver	Lungs	Kidney	Spleen	Lesion
Badger (<i>Meles meles</i>)	13	13	13	5	1			
Fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	44	45	45	4				
Cat (<i>Felis silvestris f.catus</i>)	72	72	72	2		1		
Martes (<i>Martes martes/foina</i>)	17	17	17	1				
Wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>)	42	38	41	5	7		1	1
Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)	10	10	10	7				
Raccoon dog (<i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i>)	12	12	12	4	1			
Nutria (<i>Myocastor coypus</i>)	20	19	20	6				
Deer (<i>Capreolus capreolus</i>)	6	6	5					
Squirrel (<i>Sciurus vulgaris</i>)	1	1	1					
Polecat (<i>Mustela putorius</i>)	1	1	1					
Hare (<i>Lepus europaeus</i>)	1	1	1					
Total	239	235	238	34	9	1	1	1

671 **Table 2** The list of tested pathogens, animals and tissues

Pathogen	Pathogen group	Matrix examined			672
		Faeces	Tongue	Lymph nodes	Others 673
<i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>	Parasite, protozoa,	×			
<i>Giardia duodenalis</i>	Parasite, protozoa,	×			674
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	Parasite, tapeworm	×			×
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	Parasite, protozoa,	×	×	×	675
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	Parasite, roundworm		×		×
<i>Baylisascaris procyonis</i>	Parasite, helminth	×			676
<i>Toxocara canis/cati</i>	Parasite, helminth	×			×
<i>Francisella tularensis/holarctica</i>	Bacterium		×	×	677
<i>Mycobacterium bovis</i>	Bacterium			×	×
MAP	Bacterium	×			678
MAA	Bacterium	×			
MAH	Bacterium	×			679
<i>Salmonella enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i>	Bacterium	×			
Hepatitis E virus	Virus	×			680

681 MAA: *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *avium*; MAH: *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *hominissuis*; MAP: *Mycobacterium avium* subsp.
682 *paratuberculosis*

Table 3 Primers and probes used in this study and their organization to the multiplex RT-qPCR and qPCR assays

Multiplex	Species	Name	Sequence 5' – 3'	Target gene sequence	Length (nt)	Source
HEV	Hepatitis E virus	JVHEVF	GGTGGTTTCTGGGGTGAC	Overlap of ORF3/ORF2	70	Vasickova et al., 2012
		JVHEVR	AGGGGTTGGTTGGATGAA			
		JVHEVP	FAM-TGATTCTCAGCCCTTCGC-BHQ1			
		TqFwd	CTGTTYAAAYCTTGCTGACAC	ORF2	113	
		TqRev	GTCGGCTCGCCATTGGCTGAGAC			
		Tqprobe	HEX-CCGACAGAATTGATTCGTCGGC-BHQ1			
IS900qPCRf	GATGGCCGAAGGAGATTG	Artificial	152			
IS900qPCRr	CACAACCACCTCCGTAACC					
IS900qPCRTM	Cy5-AGGCTCTTCTATGTTCTGACCTTGTGGA-BHQ1					
CGE	<i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>	hsp70F	CAAGCTGCTATCTTAAATGG	hsp70	67	Helmi et al., 2011
		hsp70R	GAGCAACATCCAATAATAAGAG			
		hsp70Pr	FAM-TGAGCAATCCTCTGCCGTACAGG -BHQ1			
CGE	<i>Giardia duodenalis</i>	β-giardinF	TCTATGTTACCTCACCCCGTAC	β-Giardin	95	
		β-giardinR	TTGCTGAGCTTGACCCGCC			
		β-giardinPr	HEX-TCACCCAGACGATGGACAAGCCC-BHQ1			
CGE	<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	EMrrnF	CTGTGATCTTGGTGTAGTAGTTGAGATTT	rrnL	84	Knapp et al., 2014
		EMrrnR	GGCTTACGCCGGTCTTAATC			
		EMrrnP	Cy5-TGGTCTGTTCCGACCTTTTAGCCCTCAT-BHQ2			
TOXTRIF	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	TgonF	TCGAAGCTGAGATGCTCAAAGTC	B1	129	Lass et al., 2012
		TgonR	AATCCACGTCTGGGAAGAAGTC			
		TgonProbe	FAM-ACCGCGAGATGCACCCGCA-BHQ1			
TOXTRIF	<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	Ts-its-spF	TGTGTGTATGATGAACAACGCG	ITS2	86	Atterby et al., 2009
		Ts-its-spR	TCATTGTCACCTGCCACACTGA			
		Ts-its-spP	HEX-TTTTATTAATGATCAGTGTGAGGTGCTGTTGTGAT-BHQ1			
TOXTRIF	<i>Francisella tularensis/holarctica</i>	FT fopA F	GCGCTTTGACTAACAAGGACA	fopA	89	Fujita et al., 2006
		FT fopA R	TCCAGCTAGACCGTTAGCATC			
		FT fopA P	Cy5-TCCTCAAGATAGAAGTGGCCAGTGG-BHQ2			
BATO	<i>Toxocara canis/cati</i>	TcanisF	GCGCCAATTTATGGAATGTGAT	ITS2	141/155	Durant et al., 2012
		TcatiF	GCGTACGTATGGAATGTGCT			
		TcaniscatiR	GAGCAAACGACAGCSATTTCTT			
		TcanisP	FAM-CCATTACCACACCAGCATAGCTCACCGA-BHQ1			
BATO	<i>Baylisascaris procyonis</i>	TcatiP	FAM-TCTTTCGCAACGTGCATTCGGTGA-BHQ1	cox-2	177	Gatcombe et al., 2010
		SrF1	GAGTTATGAGTTTAGTGATATTCCTGGA			
		JVBPR	GCAAAGCCCAAGAATGAATCAC			
MYCO		JVBPP	HEX-TATTAACATCACAAAGGTACAACAACG-BHQ1	IS901	114	
		IS901F	CCGTTGATCTGGTATCCGC			

	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> subsp. <i>avium</i>	IS901R IS901P	CGTGTGATGTTGTTGGGC FAM-CGGTCGGCAAAAAGAGCTGG-BHQ1			Dziedzinska et al., 2025
	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> subsp. <i>hominissuis</i> *	IS1245F IS1245R IS1245P	GTGGAGTGGTGAAGAGCGG AAAGTGCCGAAACCATTGCC HEX-AGCCACTATGCCGTGAGAGC-BHQ1	IS1245	96	Dziedzinska et al., 2025
	IAC	IAC F IAC R IAC P	AGAGGACCGGGATATTCGAC AGGTAGTCCGAGGAAAACCTAAAC Cy5-AGGCTCTTCTAIGTTCTGACCTTGTGGA-BHQ2	Artificial	141	Vojkowska et al., 2015
MAP	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> subsp. <i>paratuberculosis</i>	IS900qPCR IS900qPCR	GATGGCCGAAGGAGATTG CACAACCACCTCCGTAACC	IS900	145	Slana et al., 2008
		IS900qPCRTM	FAM-ATTGGATCGCTGTGTAAGGACACGT-BHQ1			
		F57qPCR F57qPCR F57qPCRTM	GCCCATTTCATCGATACC GTACCGAATGTTGTTGTCAC HEX-CAATTCTCAGCTGCAACTCGAACACAC-BHQ1	F57	147	
SEE	<i>Salmonella enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i>	ttrF ttrR ttrP	CTCACCAGGAGATTACAACATGG AGCTCAGACCAAAAGTGACCATC HEX-CACCGACGGCGAGACCGACTT-BHQ1	ttrRSBCA locus	95	Malorny et al., 2004

Table 4 Detection of pathogens and tissue distribution across animal species

Animal	Pathogen	Lungs	Liver	Tongue	Kidneys	Spleen	Intestine	Lymph nodes	Lesion	Agens-level prevalence (%)	Animal-level prevalence (%)
Badger	CRYPT	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/13 (8%)	
Badger	TOCA	0	3 ^a	--	0	0	0	--	0	3/13 (23%)	
Badger	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	1	0	--	1/13 (8%)	8/13 (62%)
Badger	MAH	--	--	--	--	--	1	0	--	1/13 (8%)	
Badger	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^a	0	--	3/13 (23%)	
Wild boar	ECMU	0	0	--	0	0	1	--	0	1/42 (2%)	
Wild boar	BAPR	--	--	--	--	--	7 ^{b,c}	--	--	7/42 (17%)	
Wild boar	FRTU	0	0	1	0	0	--	0	0	1/42 (2%)	14/42 (33%)
Wild boar	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	4 ^{a,c}	--	--	4/42 (10%)	
Wild boar	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^{a,b}	--	--	3/42 (7%)	
Wild boar	HEV	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/42 (2%)	
Cat	CRYPT	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^d	--	--	1/72 (1%)	
Cat	GIA	--	--	--	--	--	2 ^{d,f}	--	--	2/72 (3%)	
Cat	TOGO	0	0	3 ^e	0	0	0	0	0	3/72 (4%)	
Cat	BAPR	--	--	--	--	--	5 ^{b,e,g,h,i}	--	--	5/72 (7%)	
Cat	TOCA	0	0	--	0	0	22 ^{a,b,c,d,e,g,h,i}	--	0	22/72 (31%)	32/72 (44%)
Cat	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	5 ^{a,f}	--	--	5/72 (7%)	
Cat	MAH	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^f	--	--	3/72 (4%)	
Cat	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/72 (1%)	
Cat	HEV	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/72 (1%)	
Fox	CRYPT	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/45 (2%)	
Fox	TOGO	0	0	3 ^a	0	0	0	1 ^c	0	4/45 (9%)	21/45 (47%)
Fox	BAPR	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^b	--	--	3/45 (7%)	
Fox	TOCA	0	0	--	0	0	10 ^{a,b}	--	0	10/45 (22%)	

Fox	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^c	--	--	3/45 (7%)	
Fox	MAH	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/45 (2%)	
Fox	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^b	--	--	3/45 (7%)	
Marten	GIAR	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^a	--	--	1/17 (6%)	
Marten	TOGO	0	0	2 ^{a,b}	0	0	0	1	0	3/17 (18%)	
Marten	BAPR	--	--	--	--	--	5	--	--	5/17 (29%)	11/17 (65%)
Marten	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/17 (6%)	
Marten	MAH	--	--	--	--	--	2 ^b	--	--	2/17 (12%)	
Marten	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/17 (6%)	
Nutria	TOGO	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	4/20 (20%)	4/20 (20%)
Raccoon	TOCA	0	1	--	0	0	1	--	0	2/10 (20%)	
Raccoon	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^a	--	--	1/10 (10%)	
Raccoon	MAA	--	--	--	--	--	3 ^a	--	--	3/10 (30%)	7/10 (70%)
Raccoon	MAH	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^a	--	--	1/10 (10%)	
Raccoon	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	2	--	--	2/10 (20%)	
Raccoon dog	ECMU	0	2 ^{A,c}	--	0	0	1 ^A	--	0	2/12 (17%)	
Raccoon dog	TOCA	0	0	--	0	0	1 ^c	--	0	1/12 (8%)	
Raccoon dog	FRTU	0	0	1 ^D	0	0	0	1 ^D	0	1/12 (8%)	
Raccoon dog	MAP	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^b	--	--	1/12 (8%)	5/12 (42%)
Raccoon dog	MAA	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^b	--	--	1/12 (8%)	
Raccoon dog	SEE	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/12 (8%)	
Raccoon dog	HEV	--	--	--	--	--	1 ^d	--	--	1/12 (8%)	
Polecat	TOGO	0	0	1 ^A	0	0	0	1 ^A	0	1/1 (100%)	1
Squirrel	CRYPT	--	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	1/1 (100%)	1

686 Superscript lowercase letters: more different agens detected either in different or the same sample of the same animal. Superscript capital letters: the same agens detected in different organs/tissues of the same animal. 0: negative; -- not examined (non-relevant sample)

688 BAPR: *Baylisascaris procyonis*; CRYPT: *Cryptosporidium parvum*; GIAR: *Giardia duodenalis*; ECMU: *Echinococcus multilocularis*; FRTU:

689 *Francisella tularensis/holarctica*; HEV: hepatitis E virus; MAA: *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *avium*; MAH: *Mycobacterium avium* subsp.

690 *hominis*; MAP: *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis*; MB: *Mycobacterium bovis*; SEE: *Salmonella enterica* subsp. *enterica*; TOCA:
691 *Toxocara canis/cati*; TOGO: *Toxoplasma gondii*; TRSP: *Trichinella spiralis*.

Table 5 Association between age and occurrence of *Toxocara canis/cati* in red foxes

	Positive	Negative	Risk	RR	OR	p-value
Adult	4	31	0.11	0.11	0.11	-
Juvenile	6	4	0.6	5.4	11.5	0.003
Total	10	35	0.22	1.5	1.5	0.003

P-value was calculated using the Fisher exact test; OR: odds ratio; RR: risk ratio

Table 6. Pairwise Phi coefficients for pathogen co-occurrence in cats

	CRYPT	GIA	TOGO	BAPR	TOCA	MAP	MAH	SE	HEV
CRYPT		0.7*	-0.02	-0.03	0.18	-0.03	-0.02	-0.01	-0.01
GIA	0.7*		-0.04	-0.05	0.07	0.29	0.39	-0.02	-0.02
TOGO	-0.02	-0.04		-0.06	0.01	-0.06	-0.04	-0.02	-0.02
BAPR	-0.03	-0.05	-0.06		0.41**	-0.07	-0.06	-0.03	-0.03
TOCA	0.18	0.07	0.01	0.41**		-0.06	-0.14	-0.08	-0.08
MAP	-0.03	0.29	-0.06	-0.07	-0.06		0.22	-0.03	-0.03
MAH	-0.02	0.39	-0.04	-0.06	-0.14	0.22		-0.02	-0.02
SEE	-0.01	-0.02	-0.02	-0.03	-0.08	-0.03	-0.02		-0.01
HEV	-0.01	-0.02	-0.02	-0.03	-0.08	-0.03	-0.02	-0.01	

BAPR – *Baylisascaris procyonis*; CRYPT – *Cryptosporidium parvum*; GIA – *Giardia duodenalis*; HEV – hepatitis E virus; MAH – *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *hominisuis*; MAP – *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis*; SEE – *Salmonella enterica* subsp. *enterica*; TOCA – *Toxocara canis/cati*; TOGO – *Toxoplasma gondii*; * p < 0.05; ** P < 0.01

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: